

Remaining Global CO₂ Budgets

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Abstract

This document summarises the remaining global CO₂ budgets assessed in IPCC AR6 and presents updated estimates from the IGCC initiative. It explains how to interpret probabilistic budgets, clarifies the role of uncertainties and provides guidance on how policymakers can adopt precautionary interpretations of the AR6 budgets.

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What does the IPCC say about the remaining CO₂ budgets?

The goal of the [Paris Agreement](#) is to hold “the increase in the global average temperature to **well below 2°C** above pre-industrial levels” and pursue efforts “to limit the temperature increase to **1.5°C** above pre-industrial levels”.

The UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published the following figures in its Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) Working Group I 2021 (IPCC, 2021, cf. Tables SPM.2 and 5.8):

Table 1: Remaining budgets from 2020 onwards according to the IPCC (AR6)

Warming	Estimated remaining carbon budgets			Scenario variation	Geophysical uncertainties			
					Non-CO ₂ scenario variation	Non-CO ₂ forcing and response uncertainty	Historical temperature uncertainty	ZEC uncertainty
Probabilities:	50%	67%	83%					
[°C]	[GtCO ₂ from 2020 on]				[GtCO ₂]			
1.5	500	400	300	±220	±220	±550	±420	±20
1.6	650	550	400					
1.7	850	700	550					
1.8	1,000	850	650					
1.9	1,200	1,000	800					
2.0	1,350	1,150	900					

At present, the remaining CO₂ budget is being depleted by approximately **42 GtCO₂ annually**.¹

A web app for calculating linear emission pathways consistent with a given CO₂ budget is available at (temporary overshooting can be taken into account): <https://global-paths.climate-calculator.info>.

The IPCC writes about the CO₂ budget (IPCC, 2021, p. 28 f., emphasis and [...] not in the original):

«**D.1.1** [...] there is a **near-linear relationship between cumulative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and the global warming they cause**. Each 1000 GtCO₂ of cumulative CO₂ emissions is assessed to likely cause a 0.27°C to 0.63°C increase in global surface temperature with a best estimate of 0.45°C. [...] This quantity is referred to as the transient climate response to cumulative CO₂ emissions (TCRE). This relationship implies that reaching net zero anthropogenic CO₂ emissions is a requirement to stabilize human-induced global temperature increase at any level, but that **limiting global temperature increase to a specific level would imply limiting cumulative CO₂ emissions to within a carbon budget**.»

«**D.1.2** [...] **Remaining carbon budgets have been estimated for several global temperature limits and various levels of probability**, based on the estimated value of TCRE and its uncertainty, estimates of historical warming [±550 GtCO₂], variations in projected warming from non-CO₂ emissions [±220 GtCO₂], climate system feedbacks such as emissions from thawing permafrost [±220 GtCO₂], and the global surface temperature change after global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions reach net zero [ZEC].»

Regarding **probabilities**, the IPCC notes (IPCC, 2021, p. 29, emphasis and [...] not in the original):²

«This likelihood is based on the uncertainty in transient climate response to cumulative CO₂ emissions (TCRE) and additional Earth system feedbacks and provides the probability that global warming will not exceed the temperature levels [...]. Uncertainties related to historical warming (±550 GtCO₂) and non-CO₂ forcing and response (±220 GtCO₂) are **partially addressed** by the **assessed uncertainty in TCRE**, but uncertainties in recent emissions since 2015 (±20 GtCO₂) and the climate response after net zero CO₂ emissions are reached (±420 GtCO₂) **are separate**.»

¹ See Table 4 for actual emissions after 2019.

² The reddish marking of fields in Table 1 is intended to indicate that only in cases of high probability can a serious pursuit of the corresponding target be assumed, and what a significant reduction below 2 °C would entail.

Updated budgets

Since 2023, the Indicators of Global Climate Change ([IGCC](#)) initiative has published an annual update on remaining CO₂ budgets, which also takes into account the latest scientific findings. IGCC publishes the remaining budgets (see Table 2), also taking into account known actual emissions from 2020 onwards (cf. Forster, P.M. et al., 2026). Table 3 shows the results converted to budgets from 2020 onwards. For this conversion, budget-relevant CO₂ emissions for 2020–2025 were added (see Table 4).

Table 2: Updated budgets from 2026 onwards (IGCC)

Warming	Estimated remaining carbon budgets			
	Probabilities:	50%	67%	83%
[°C]	[GtCO ₂ from 2026 on]			
1.5	130	80	30	10
1.6	320	240	170	130
1.7	500	390	300	250
1.8	680	550	430	370
1.9	860	700	560	480
2.0	1,050	860	690	600

Table 3: Recalculated updated budgets from 2020 onwards

Warming	Estimated remaining carbon budgets				
	IGCC				IPCC AR6
Probabilities:	50%	67%	83%	90%	83%
[°C]	[GtCO ₂ from 2020 on]				
1.5	378	328	278	258	300
1.6	568	488	418	378	400
1.7	748	638	548	498	550
1.8	928	798	678	618	650
1.9	1,108	948	808	728	800
2.0	1,298	1,108	938	848	900

Table 4: Actual emissions from 2020 onwards³

GtCO ₂	GCP			IGCC source values			GCP	IGCC incl. CeCS	EDGAR		
	fossil	LUC	total	fossil	LULUCF	total	CeCS	total	fossil	LULUCF	total
2020	34.4	4.5	38.9	35.2	4.5	39.7	-0.8	38.9	36.2	-0.11	36.1
2021	36.0	4.7	40.7	36.9	4.7	41.5	-0.8	40.7	38.2	-0.35	37.9
2022	36.7	4.8	41.5	37.5	4.8	42.3	-0.8	41.5	38.5	-0.24	38.3
2023	37.3	4.7	42.0	38.1	4.7	42.8	-0.8	42.0	39.1	1.30	40.4
2024	37.8	4.6	42.4	38.6	4.6	43.2	-0.8	42.4	39.6	-0.05	39.6
subtotal	182.2	23.3	205.5	186.2	23.3	209.5	-4.1	205.5	191.7	0.5	192.3
2025	38.1	4.1	42.2								
total			247.7								

³ Notes: The annual GCP totals are used for the conversion of the IGCC budgets to a 2020 base year (GCP, 2025). The IGCC source values shown here are CO₂-FFI plus CO₂-LULUCF before accounting for the cement carbonation sink; the CeCS adjustment reconciles them with the GCP totals used here. EDGAR's LULUCF estimates are not directly comparable to GCP or IGCC due to different system boundaries (EDGAR, 2025). Therefore, EDGAR total emissions should not be used for budget accounting. The emissions for 2025 at GCP are a projection.

Interpretation of the IPCC budgets

The probabilistic budgets reported in IPCC AR6 (50%, 67%, 83%) reflect uncertainty in TCRE, as well as uncertainties that are partially addressed through it — in particular those related to historical warming and non-CO₂ forcing.

However, two additional sources of physical uncertainty — Zero-Emissions Commitment (ZEC)⁴ and recent-emissions uncertainty⁵ — are not included in these probabilistic estimates.

The IPCC therefore reports ZEC-related uncertainty separately as ± 420 GtCO₂, centred around a best estimate of approximately zero. This implies that the ZEC range should not be applied arithmetically to the AR6 carbon budget values. ZEC therefore widens the range of possible realized temperature outcomes without altering the central AR6 budget values. A precautionary interpretation can therefore be achieved by orienting policy towards lower temperature thresholds at higher probability levels.

In contrast to these physical uncertainties, the ‘scenario variation’ term reflects scenario-dependent differences and, like ZEC and recent-emissions uncertainty, is not part of the probabilistic budgets.⁶ The ± 220 GtCO₂ variation reflects the spread of non-CO₂ mitigation pathways across the scenario ensembles used in AR6 that are compatible with 1.5 °C or 2 °C. Departures from the assumed non-CO₂ trajectory will therefore lead to systematically different CO₂ budgets.

AR6 budgets are best-estimate values, not boundaries that incorporate all sources of Earth-system uncertainty.

Example of an IPCC-consistent statement for an 83% likelihood of limiting warming to 1.8 °C

For an 83% probability of limiting the increase in global mean surface temperature to **1.8 °C**, the IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) assesses a remaining carbon budget of **approximately 650 GtCO₂ from 2020 onwards** (IPCC, 2021, cf. Tables SPM.2 and 5.8). When incorporating the IGCC update, the corresponding estimate amounts to 678 GtCO₂ (see Chapter “Updated budgets”).

This probabilistic budget reflects uncertainties in TCRE, including those related to historical warming and non-CO₂ forcing through the assessed TCRE range. This statement also assumes a compatible non-CO₂ emissions trajectory. For ZEC, the best available estimator of zero is presumed.

⁴ ZEC arises from physical processes that govern the climate response after net-zero CO₂ emissions are reached, including continued ocean heat uptake, slow feedbacks (e.g. permafrost–carbon interactions), and the adjustment of non-CO₂ forcing. Because the magnitude and sign of these post-net-zero processes are uncertain, IPCC AR6 reports ZEC as a separate physical uncertainty rather than integrating it into the probabilistic remaining carbon budgets.

⁵ Recent-emissions uncertainty refers to uncertainties in the historical emissions data that determine how much of the remaining carbon budget has already been used. It is classified as a physical Earth-system uncertainty because it affects the diagnosed state of the climate system, not future scenario assumptions.

⁶ AR6 remaining CO₂ budgets are conditional on the median non-CO₂ pathway of the 1.5 °C — or 2 °C — compatible mitigation scenarios. The probabilistic (50%, 67%, 83%) budgets incorporate physical uncertainty in the climatic response to non-CO₂ forcing—partly represented through the TCRE range—but do not include uncertainty in future non-CO₂ emissions. Any deviation from the assumed non-CO₂ pathway would therefore alter the remaining CO₂ budget.

References

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